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University of Helsinki

Anchors as Weapons: Chinese Maritime Grey-Zone Operations and the Limits of European Hybrid Threat Frameworks

Julie Yu-Wen Chen, Professor of Chinese Studies, University of Helsinki

Julie.chen@helsinki.fi

Abstract

Existing typologies of Chinese influence in Europe organise activities into four categories: economic leverage, elite capture, information manipulation, and critical infrastructure positioning. This paper argues that Baltic Sea cable incidents since 2023 require a fifth — physical grey-zone operations — that existing frameworks cannot capture. Drawing on structured focused comparison of the Newnew Polar Bear (2023) and Yi Peng 3 (2024) cases, supplemented by comparison with Taiwan cable disruptions, the paper shows that Chinese-linked vessels deployed anchor-dragging combining deliberate infrastructure damage, commercial proxy instrumentalisation, and systematic deniability architecture exploiting flag-state jurisdiction. Process tracing finds the cumulative evidence substantially more consistent with deliberate disruption than accident. The paper further identifies an emergent Russia-China nexus that single-actor frameworks cannot address, and develops policy implications across four domains: jurisdictional reform, intelligence and attribution, deterrence, and diplomatic engagement with Beijing. The analysis contributes a revised typology and

actionable framework for European policymakers.

Keywords: Chinese influence typologies; physical grey-zone operations; undersea cable disruption; Baltic Sea security; Sino-Russian coordination; Taiwan

1. Introduction

The study of Chinese influence in Europe has grown substantially since the mid-2010s, driven by a convergence of policy alarm and scholarly interest. Economic and informational dimensions have attracted considerable attention — Belt and Road Initiative (BRI) investment leverage, elite capture, and foreign information manipulation — and the literature on these is now mature (e.g., Benner et al. 2018; Chen 2020; Aukia 2021; Hackenbroich, Medunic, and Zerka 2022; Chen and Ristivojević 2023; MERICS 2023; Bonnet et al. 2026; Bachulska, Karásková, and Szatters 2026). The physical and maritime dimensions, however, remain analytically underdeveloped. This paper argues that undersea cable incidents in the Baltic Sea since 2023 represent an emergent and distinct form of Chinese influence that existing frameworks are ill-equipped to capture, and that their inclusion requires a revised typology of Chinese influence in Europe.

Existing conceptual frameworks for understanding Chinese state behaviour below the threshold of military force — from soft power (Nye 2004) to sharp power (Walker and Ludwig 2017; Walker, Kalathil, and Ludwig 2020) — are primarily oriented toward cognitive and informational manipulation. Sharp power, in particular, has been influential in capturing how authoritarian states pierce and distort the political and information environments of open

societies, but it has no analytical purchase on physical disruption. This paper therefore positions itself within the hybrid threat literature rather than the sharp power tradition. The European Centre of Excellence for Countering Hybrid Threats (Hybrid CoE) defines hybrid activities as the coordinated use of multiple tools — military, economic, informational, cyber, and administrative — to achieve political objectives while remaining below the threshold of armed conflict and maintaining plausible deniability (Aukia 2021). This framework, extended here to Chinese actors rather than its usual Russian referent, better captures the physical dimension of the Baltic incidents. A related strand comes from strategic studies literature on grey-zone operations — actions defined by their ambiguity, cost-imposition logic, and deliberate avoidance of attribution thresholds (Mazarr 2015; Brands 2016) — which has been applied to Chinese behaviour in the South China Sea and Taiwan Strait but not yet systematically to European waters (Erickson and Martinson 2019).

Two Baltic Sea incidents anchor empirical analysis. In October 2023, the Chinese-flagged Newnew Polar Bear severed the Balticconnector gas pipeline and associated data cables between Finland and Estonia — damage later admitted by China but attributed to a storm (Bermingham 2024; ERR 2024). In November 2024, the Chinese carrier Yi Peng 3 dragged its anchor for 180 nautical miles across the Baltic seabed, severing two fibre-optic cables connecting Finland-Germany and Sweden-Lithuania, in a month-long diplomatic standoff that ended with European investigators permitted on board only as observers of a Chinese-led inquiry. The Swedish Accident Investigation Authority (Statens haverikommission, SHK, 2025) concluded there was no definitive proof of deliberate intent, while simultaneously noting that some facts to a certain extent contradict the unintentional damage explanation. Neither case has yielded evidence of state-directed sabotage. Together, however, they constitute a pattern — reinforced by analogous Chinese-linked cable disruptions around Taiwan since 2021 — that existing typologies of Chinese influence were not designed to investigate.

This paper makes three contributions. First, it proposes a fifth category in the typology of Chinese influence in Europe — physical grey-zone operations — defined by physical mechanism, proxy instrumentalisation through commercial shipping, and systematic deniability architecture exploiting flag-state jurisdiction under the United Nations Convention on the Law of the Sea (UNCLOS). Second, it applies structured focused comparison and process tracing to the Baltic cases as international relations problems, providing methodological rigour absent from existing legal analyses and policy commentary on these incidents (e.g., Besh and Brown 2024; Sari 2025; Chiang 2025; Stockholm International Peace Research Institute, SIPRI, 2025). Third, it identifies and theorises an emergent Russia-China nexus dimension in Baltic maritime disruption that neither the Chinese influence nor the Russian hybrid warfare literature currently addresses (e.g., Renz 2016; Fridman 2018; Joske 2022). The paper is explicitly theory-building rather than theory-testing: the goal is to propose an analytical framework adequate to the phenomenon, not to deliver a definitive attribution verdict that the available evidence does not support.

The paper proceeds as follows. Section 2 reviews the existing typology of Chinese influence in Europe and identifies the gap that motivates the paper's contribution. Section 3 presents the methodology. Section 4 applies structured focused comparison to the Newnew Polar Bear case, the Yi Peng 3 case, and the Taiwan reference case. Section 5 proposes revised typology. Section 6 derives policy implications across four domains: legal and jurisdictional reform, intelligence and attribution, deterrence and response, and diplomatic engagement with China. Section 7 concludes with directions for future research.

2. Literature Review: Current Typology and Its Limits

The dominant typology of Chinese influence in Europe organises activities into four potentially interlinked categories: economic and financial influence; political and elite capture; information

operations and foreign information manipulation and interference (FIMI); and infrastructure-as-positioning (e.g., Benner et al. 2018; Aukia 2021; Hackenbroich, Medunic, and Zerka 2022; MERICS 2023; Bonnet et al. 2026; Bachulska, Karásková, and Szatters 2026). This section surveys each category, identifies their shared analytical limitation, and argues that the Baltic cable incidents expose a structured gap that requires a fifth category — physical grey-zone operations — which no existing peer-reviewed work has yet proposed.

2.1 Economic and Financial Influence

China's economic influence in Europe is well studied. China exercises economic power in Europe through five interlocking channels: a massive trade deficit (€312 billion in 2024, rising to €360 billion in 2025) (European Commission 2026a), supply chain dependencies in batteries, rare earths, and Electric Vehicles (EV) components that function as silent coercion (Bonnet et al. 2026) — firms self-censor politically when they assess that a policy decision risks endangering components or market access. China also has port ownership across Belgium, Germany, Greece, Italy, the Netherlands, and Spain, and deliberate political targeting of investment and retaliation (MERICS 2023). Hungary alone absorbed 31 per cent of all Chinese foreign direct investment (FDI) in the European Union (EU) and United Kingdom (UK) in 2024, and Beijing's use of frameworks like 16+1 and BRI has raised concerns that strategic asset acquisition expands China's capacity to divide and rule the continent (Chen and Hao 2020). When European policy challenges Chinese interests, retaliation follows precise political logic: after the EU voted to impose EV tariffs in October 2024, China launched anti-dumping investigations into EU pork, dairy, and brandy, targeting politically sensitive agricultural sectors to maximise internal EU division. Economic leverage and political influence are, in China's approach, designed to reinforce each other (Hackenbroich, Medunic, and Zerka 2022; Bonnet et al. 2026).

2.2 Political and Elite Capture

The political influence literature is also rich. Benner et al.'s (2018) *Authoritarian Advance* suggests systematic Chinese Communist Party (CCP) engagement across European media, academia, think tanks, and political parties to promote favourable narratives and reduce critical scrutiny. The Prague-based MapInfluenCE (2026) project provides the most systematic country-by-country documentation of Chinese FIMI across Central and Eastern Europe (CEE), distinguishing media influence, political capture, and economic inducement. Oertel (2020) found growing awareness of Chinese influence tactics among European political elites. A consistent finding across this literature is that Chinese influence in CEE exploits institutional weaknesses and political fragmentation in ways less available in more consolidated Western European democracies.

2.3 Information Manipulation and Cyber Operations

The informational dimension of Chinese influence has grown as a research area since 2019–2020, partly driven by COVID-19-related disinformation campaigns and increasing EU institutional attention. The European External Action Service's (EEAS) annual FIMI reports (2026) document Chinese information manipulation alongside Russian operations, noting that Chinese FIMI is generally more focused on narrative promotion than active fabrication, and harder to attribute. China's preference for content amplification through state media (CGTN, Xinhua, Global Times) and co-opted local intermediaries — rather than troll farms — distinguishes it from its Russian equivalent (Aukia 2021; Bachulska, Karásková, and Szatters 2026). Distinct but related, Chinese cyber operations in Europe — including the APT31 campaign against the Czech Foreign Ministry, publicly attributed by Prague and supported by the North Atlantic Treaty Organisation (NATO 2025) — situate cyber activity within a broader spectrum of below-threshold operation. What the information and cyber literature share is a

cognitive orientation: they are designed to shape perceptions and degrade trust rather than to impose physical costs. This cognitive focus is a structural limitation for this paper's purposes, as it leaves physical disruption analytically unaddressed.

2.4 Infrastructure-as-Positioning

A fourth strand examines Chinese investment in European critical infrastructure — ports, energy networks, 5G, and undersea cables — as a vector of strategic vulnerability. The European Parliament's 2023 briefing analyses Chinese state-linked entities' involvement through the lens of military-civil fusion (MCF), noting that China's party-led system does not permit clear distinctions between commercial and military interests. Carnegie Endowment for International Peace's (Besh and Brown 2024) *Securing Europe's Subsea Data Cables* provides the most thorough European treatment of cable infrastructure specifically, tracing European policymakers' slow recognition of Chinese cable manufacturing and installation as a security risk. The key analytical characteristic of this strand is its latency logic: Chinese infrastructure presence is analysed as a capability that could be activated for coercive purposes, not as an instrument of active disruption. This latency assumption, appropriate before 2023, has been overtaken by events.

2.5 From Ownership to Disruption: The Baltic Cable Incidents

The specific phenomenon of Chinese-linked physical disruption to European undersea infrastructure is recent enough that academic literature is sparse; most analysis exists in policy reports and investigative journalism. This scarcity is itself analytically significant — it marks the boundary of the existing typology and defines the space this paper seeks to occupy.

The Newnew Polar Bear incident of October 2023 and the Yi Peng 3 incident of November 2024 (detailed in Section 4) are not isolated incidents. The China Strategic Risks Institute (Yeh

2025) documented twelve suspected undersea cable sabotage cases across Europe between January 2021 and April 2025, of which eight involved vessels linked to China or Russia by flag or ownership. Parallel cable disruptions around Taiwan — including twelve cuts in 2023 alone — exhibit the same anchor-drag mechanism and deniability template. This cross-regional pattern-level evidence, not yet systematically engaged in academic literature, is the empirical foundation of this paper's argument.

No academic literature has proposed a typology that positions physical grey-zone operations as a distinct and analytically separable category of Chinese influence in Europe. The closest contributions are either legal analyses — Ringbom and Lott (2024) and Ringbom (2025) — which address jurisdictional questions but not international relations or hybrid threat typology, or policy commentary — the Global Taiwan Institute (Chiang 2025) and Carnegie Endowment (Besh and Brown 2024) — which apply a grey-zone framing descriptively without structured methodology or engagement with the Chinese influence typology literature. Second, the attribution methodology specific to maritime infrastructure incidents — how intent is established under conditions of commercial vessel proxy use, plausible deniability, and restricted investigative access — has not been theorised in relation to Chinese actors, despite the development of comparable frameworks in the Russian hybrid warfare literature (Murphy and Schaub 2018; Praks 2025). Third, the Russia-China coordination dimension of Baltic cable incidents has not been systematically examined in either the Russia-China relations literature (Stent 2020; Chen and Taylor 2026) or the EU hybrid threat literature (Cullen et al. 2021).

This paper addresses these three gaps. It does not claim that cable cutting is a deliberate Chinese state policy — the evidence does not support such a conclusion, and asserting it would overreach the data. Its aim is narrower: to show that the observable pattern is analytically distinct from existing categories of Chinese influence, that current frameworks are inadequate for examining it, and that new methodological and conceptual tools are needed. This is a theory-

building contribution (George and Bennett 2005), not a causal verdict. The next section outlines the methodology used to pursue this research goal.

3. Methodology

The methodology section consists of four parts. First, we outline the structured focused comparison and its five analytical dimensions. Second, we explain the case-selection strategy. Third, we describe the process-tracing approach. Fourth, we introduce the various data sources on which the analysis relies.

3.1 Structured Focused Comparison

The primary method is structured focused comparison (George and Bennett 2005), a form of comparative case study designed for small-N research where the goal is to identify causal mechanisms rather than establish statistical correlation. The method is 'structured' in that the researcher writes general questions that reflect the research objective and asks these questions of each case under study, thereby guiding and standardising data collection and making systematic comparison possible. The method is focused in that it deals only with certain aspects of the cases examined (George and Bennett 2005).

The following five dimensions of questions are applied identically to each case. They operationalise the study's focus and ensure genuine comparability across cases: (1) physical facts and vessel behaviour; (2) attribution process and access management; (3) evidentiary outcome and residual ambiguity; (4) diplomatic and policy response; and (5) fit with the grey-zone disruption framework. Each functions as both an empirical question and a test, assessing whether the observable sequence is more consistent with deliberate grey-zone disruption or commercial accident.

3.2 Case Selection

Three cases are examined, each selected for a distinct analytical purpose as shown in Table 1.

Table 1. Case Selection

Case	Incident	Status	Analytical purpose
Case A	Newnew Polar Bear (Oct 2023)	Chinese responsibility admitted; intent disputed	Establishes baseline; reveals structural attribution problem
Case B	Yi Peng 3 (Nov 2024)	Strong circumstantial evidence; legally unresolved; Russia link alleged	Primary theory-building case; richest source of mechanism evidence
Reference	Taiwan cables (2021–2025)	Chinese involvement less contested in existing literature	Cross-regional external validity check; strengthens pattern argument

Case A (Newnew Polar Bear, October 2023) is the first confirmed instance of Chinese-linked physical disruption to European undersea infrastructure, establishing the baseline attribution template. Case B (Yi Peng 3, November 2024) is the primary analytical case — most extensively documented, diplomatically consequential, and analytically complex. The Taiwan reference case (2021–2025) provides a cross-regional external validity check; it is not subjected to full process tracing (see Section 3.4) and functions as a structural comparator, not a co-equal case.

3.3 Within-Case Analysis: Process Tracing

Alongside the cross-case comparison, each case is subjected to within-case process tracing (Van Evera 1997; Bennett 2010). Process tracing examines the sequence of events and decisions within a single case to assess whether they are consistent with a proposed causal mechanism —

in this instance, whether the sequence of vessel behaviour, deniability management, and diplomatic response is consistent with deliberate grey-zone disruption versus accidental damage followed by routine diplomatic management.

Process tracing employs four types of evidentiary test, following Van Evera (1997) and Bennett (2010) (Table 2). First, the hoop test for the grey-zone hypothesis requires that several conditions must be present for the deliberate disruption hypothesis to remain viable. These include: the vessel was in a location where anchor dragging would predictably intersect with known cable routes (publicly documented in nautical charts); weather and sea conditions at the time were insufficient to cause unintentional anchor loss; the vessel's Automatic Identification System (AIS) shows anomalies inconsistent with routine commercial passage; and China resisted or constrained external investigative access to the vessel.

The smoking gun test means that evidence would strongly confirm China's deliberate intent if we can find: (1) communications evidence linking the crew or ownership chain to state or intelligence actors; (2) navigation data showing deliberate course alteration to intersect cable routes; and (3) evidence of prior intelligence on cable locations beyond publicly available nautical charts. In this paper, smoking gun evidence is not available — which is consistent with effective deniability management and does not constitute evidence of innocence.

Table 2. Four Types of Evidentiary Test

Test	Logic	If evidence present	If evidence absent	Cases
Hoop test	Evidence that must be present for hypothesis to survive	Hypothesis not eliminated; no major confirmation	Hypothesis eliminated	Used and passed in all cases

Test	Logic	If evidence present	If evidence absent	Cases
Smoking gun test	Evidence that, if found, strongly confirms hypothesis	Hypothesis strongly confirmed	Hypothesis not eliminated	Hard to implement in all cases
Straw-in-the-wind test	Suggestive but inconclusive evidence	Slight increase in confidence	Slight decrease in confidence	Used and passed in all cases
Doubly decisive test	Conclusive regardless of outcome	Hypothesis confirmed, alternatives eliminated	Hypothesis eliminated, alternatives confirmed	Hard to implement in all cases

Sources: Van Evera (1997) and Bennett (2010).

The straw-in-the-wind test involves circumstantial information that hints at a possible explanation or future event but is not definitive. It is consistent with a hypothesis, but because it could also fit other explanations, it does not definitively prove or disprove anything.

A fourth test type — the doubly decisive test, in which a single piece of evidence would conclusively confirm or eliminate the hypothesis regardless of outcome — is not applied in this paper. That omission is deliberate and analytically informative: a doubly decisive test requires access to the Voyage Data Recorder (VDR) data, navigation logs, and crew communications held on board the suspect vessels. China denied European investigators access to precisely this material in both cases. The systematic deniability architecture that defines the fifth category is specifically designed to prevent doubly decisive evidence from reaching external investigators. Its inapplicability is therefore not a methodological weakness but a diagnostic feature of the phenomenon: physical grey-zone operations are constructed to resist conclusive evidentiary standards.

3.4 Data Sources and Triangulation

Table 3 summarises four types of data sources: (1) open-source intelligence (OSINT) and AIS tracking; (2) official investigation reports and government statements; (3) policy analysis; and (4) verified media and investigative journalistic reports. Given China's increasing restriction of access to domestic databases and the inherently covert nature of the activity under study, the paper relies on triangulation across these sources. Triangulation reduces dependence on any single source and helps identify where accounts converge (increasing confidence) or diverge (flagging interpretive uncertainty for explicit discussion).

Table 3. Data Sources and Triangulation

Source type	Key examples	Analytical role
Open-source intelligence (OSINT) / vessel tracking	MarineTraffic AIS data; used by Reuters, Swedish authorities, independent analysts	Primary for vessel behaviour; AIS anomalies analytically significant
Official investigation records	Swedish SHK report; police statements; parliamentary inquiries	Primary; most authoritative but diplomatically constrained
Policy and think-tank analysis	Swedish National China Centre; SIPRI; Carnegie Endowment; Hybrid CoE	Secondary; contextualises official findings within strategic frameworks
Media reports and investigative journalism	Reuters; Wall Street Journal; Swedish broadcaster SVT; Finnish broadcaster YLE	Secondary; accesses sources unavailable in official records; subject to source evaluation

Owing to space constraints, Section 4 presents only a selective set of references. Numerous additional sources are available in open-access outlets. With this clarification, the paper now

proceeds to the empirical analysis.

4. Empirical Analysis

The empirical analysis presents the three cases across five analytical dimensions in the following subsections, followed by a cross-case synthesis in Section 4.4.

4.1 Case A: Newnew Polar Bear (October 2023)

Concerning physical facts and vessel behaviour, on the night of 7–8 October 2023 the 77-kilometre Balticconnector pipeline between Paldiski (Estonia) and Inkoo (Finland) was severed, along with the EES1 Estonia–Sweden telecommunications cable and a third cable linking St. Petersburg to Russia's Baltic exclave of Kaliningrad. The event triggered automatic shutdowns and a joint Finnish–Estonian response (Bermingham 2024). AIS data analysed by Reuters (Lehto 2023) and Finnish authorities (Poliisi 2023) placed the Newnew Polar Bear — a Hong Kong-flagged container ship owned by Hainan Yangpu NewNew Ship Management Co. — at the damage site around 01:20 on 8 October. The vessel slowed but did not stop, and Finnish investigators confirmed it was missing a front anchor consistent with the recovered one. The Norwegian Seismic Array reported blast-like seismic waves at the relevant time (NORSAR 2023). The Russian nuclear-powered Sevmorput was also in the vicinity. Notably, the Newnew Polar Bear had been renamed and reregistered in Hong Kong in June 2023, having previously sailed as Baltic Fulmar under a Cypriot flag — a timing consistent with, though not probative of, preparation for a covert operation (Radio Free Asia 2023).

On attribution process and access management, the vessel did not respond to repeated Finnish contact attempts and instead sailed through Russian territorial waters back to China, preventing boarding or inspection. China's Ministry of Foreign Affairs stated in 2023 that communication with Finland was open and smooth and expressed willingness to assist in line with international

law, while urging an objective and impartial investigation (Ministry of Foreign Affairs of the People's Republic of China 2023). However, Beijing did not act on formal legal-aid requests, leaving its investigation internal and inadmissible under Finnish law. In August 2024 — nearly ten months after the incident — China acknowledged that the Newnew Polar Bear caused the damage, attributing it to a severe storm (Bermingham 2024). Estonian and Finnish authorities stressed that the Chinese report did not qualify as official evidence (YLE 2024), and China still had not responded to legal-aid requests or made crew available for questioning (ERR 2024; Poliisi 2025; Torode and Pomfret 2026).

Regarding evidentiary outcome and residual ambiguity, Finnish investigators established beyond reasonable doubt that the ship's anchor caused the damage. The remaining uncertainty concerns intent. China's storm explanation has been questioned by maritime experts (Helsingin Sanomat 2024): weather conditions were mild (Humpert 2025); unintentionally losing a multitonne anchor without crew awareness is technically implausible; and a drag trail extending dozens of nautical miles should have produced detectable vibration and noise. The AIS slowdown could reflect anchor drag, deliberate manoeuvring, or routine adjustment. Sevmorput's presence has been noted but not developed into a formal finding. The overall outcome is confirmed physical causation, unresolved intent, and a contested but not disproven Chinese explanation — consistent with deliberate ambiguity.

In terms of diplomatic and policy response, European governments reacted cautiously. The incident was initially framed through concerns about Russian hybrid activity, given the Nord Stream precedent and Baltic security context (Kallionpää 2023). Finland and Estonia opened criminal investigations constrained by China's non-cooperation; no EU-level response followed. The Balticconnector was repaired by May 2024. The incident accelerated EU work on critical-infrastructure protection and prompted strengthened Baltic maritime-security coordination among Finland, Sweden, and Germany (European Commission 2023; President of the Republic

of Finland 2025).

As for the fit with the grey-zone operation framework, the case meets most hoop tests: the vessel's position at the cable intersection is confirmed; weather conditions contradict the storm claim; AIS anomalies are present; and China resisted external investigative access. Smoking-gun tests are unmet, with no direct evidence of intent or state direction. Straw-in-the-wind indicators — the vessel's renaming and reregistration shortly before the incident; its anomalous routing through Russian waters; and weather conditions inconsistent with China's explanation — are individually inconclusive but collectively suggestive. Case A thus establishes a template of confirmed damage, disputed intent, investigative obstruction, and an implausible but unrefuted Chinese narrative, against which Case B is interpreted.

4.2 Case B: Yi Peng 3 (November 2024)

The Yi Peng 3 incident of November 2024 is the most analytically consequential case of maritime infrastructure damage in European waters, combining extraordinary physical facts, complex attribution dynamics, and a high-stakes diplomatic standoff. On 17 November, the BCS East–West Interlink cable between Sweden and Lithuania was severed; 18 hours later, the CLion1 cable between Finland and Germany was also cut, both in Swedish territorial waters. AIS data placed the Yi Peng 3 — a Chinese-flagged carrier owned by Ningbo Yipeng Shipping Co. — directly over both sites at the relevant times (SHK 2025). According to the SHK's April 2025 report, the vessel's anchor dragged 180 nautical miles over 36 hours, an 'extraordinary finding' essentially incompatible with normal seamanship negligence, as such drag would be unmistakable to any competent officer (SHK 2025).

Attribution unfolded in three phases: rapid identification, a month-long standoff, and a restricted inspection. After departing Ust-Luga on 15 November, the vessel anchored in the Kattegat on 19 November, where it remained surrounded by Danish, German, and Swedish

vessels. Because the ship sailed under the Chinese flag, European authorities could not compel boarding without Beijing's consent. Sweden formally requested access to the VDR and surveillance footage in late November (SHK 2025). Only after prolonged negotiation did China permit a Chinese-led inspection in late December, with European investigators limited to observation. They were denied access to electronic data, crew interviews under Swedish procedure, and timely physical inspection. As the SHK noted, 'investigators had not been able to access surveillance images or the VDR,' and the delay reduced evidentiary value (SHK 2025). The ship then sailed on to Port Said.

The SHK's evidentiary conclusions were deliberately cautious: it confirmed the anchor caused the damage but found no conclusive proof of intent — while explicitly stating it could not rule out deliberate action. Crucially, the report attributed its inability to reach a definitive conclusion to China's restricted-access conditions. In parallel, Western intelligence assessments — reported by the Wall Street Journal (Pancevski 2024a, 2024c) and echoed by US Assistant Secretary of Defense Christopher Maier (US Indo-Pacific Command 2024) — judged that the Chinese captain had been induced by Russian intelligence to deploy the anchor (Humpert 2024), introducing a Russia–China nexus distinct from both the 'Chinese sabotage' and 'commercial accident' hypotheses.

Diplomatically, the response was far more forceful than in the Newnew Polar Bear case, reflecting both the scale of the damage (four NATO members affected) and Europe's heightened threat perception. China combined formulaic cooperation language with substantive obstruction, presenting its month-long management of the standoff as goodwill (Ministry of Foreign Affairs of the People's Republic of China 2024) while preventing European prosecutors from obtaining prosecutable evidence. This pattern — performative compliance paired with investigative obstruction — aligns with grey-zone deniability management. The incident also accelerated EU and Nordic cable-security legislation; Finland's seizure of the Russian tanker Eagle S on

Christmas Day 2024 (Rajavartiolaitos, Finnish Border Guard, 2024) demonstrated a sharper regional enforcement posture. The EU Cable Security Toolbox (European Commission 2026b) was directly catalysed by this cumulative pattern.

The case passes the hoop test for grey-zone operations more strongly than any other European cable incident. The vessel's presence at both damage sites is confirmed; the 180-nautical-mile anchor drag is incompatible with accidental deployment; the 7 November speed reduction near Danish–Swedish cables is consistent with reconnaissance; and China's investigative obstruction fits deliberate deniability protection. No smoking gun has been publicly produced, but the Western intelligence assessment remains the closest approximation.

The straw-in-the-wind indicators further raise the probability of deliberate action: (1) the vessel shifted from exclusively Asian operations to Russian port calls in 2024 (SHK 2025); (2) it slowed and altered course near Kattegat cables on 7 November (SHK 2025); (3) it departed Ust-Luga carrying Russian fertiliser two days before the first cut (Raza 2024); and (4) the captain was reportedly a Russian citizen (Bryant and Sauer 2024), with a Russian Black Sea Fleet corvette conducting reconnaissance in the area (Pancevski 2024b). Together, these suggest the vessel operated within a Russia-linked network of intent.

Overall, the Yi Peng 3 incident provides the strongest available evidence of grey-zone maritime operation in Europe: extraordinary physical facts, systematic access obstruction, and intelligence assessments pointing toward coordinated Russian–Chinese involvement. The Swedish National China Centre's 2025 analysis (Andersson, Jerdén, and von Sydow 2025) concluded that evidence cannot distinguish between hypotheses ranging from Chinese central direction to lower-level Russia–China coordination, but even the most limited scenario — Russian actors inducing a Chinese crew without central authorisation — would carry significant implications for understanding hybrid operational cooperation in Europe.

4.3 Reference Case: Taiwan Undersea Cable Incidents (2021–2025)

The Taiwan reference case tests whether the causal pattern identified in the Baltic — Chinese-linked anchor dragging, cable damage, and deniability management — generalises beyond the European context. Taiwan is not subjected to full process tracing because its function is comparative, its evidentiary base is thinner (no SHK-type reports, no detailed AIS reconstructions, no access-management records), and attribution is more politically contested. It therefore serves as a cross-regional probe rather than a co-equal case.

Cable damage around Taiwan since 2023 is far above global accident rates. Taiwan recorded 36 externally caused incidents between 2019 and 2023 (Marine Insight 2025). In February 2023, two Matsu cables were severed by a Chinese fishing boat and a Chinese cargo vessel. In January 2025, the Chinese-owned Shunxin 39 — operating under two flags and six Maritime Mobile Service Identity (MMSI) numbers — damaged cable cores near northern Taiwan; a deputy digital affairs minister described the act as 'almost certainly intentional' (Wang 2025). In February 2025, the Togo-flagged, Chinese-crewed Hong Tai 58 severed Chunghwa Telecom's Penghu cable, leading to Taiwan's first cable-sabotage conviction in June 2025 (Ewe and Chiang 2025; Marine Insight 2025). All incidents involved anchor dragging or deliberate cable contact, directly paralleling the Baltic mechanism.

Attribution dynamics differ structurally from the Baltic because Taiwan lacks diplomatic relations with China and therefore cannot pursue flag-state cooperation. China's responses have been limited to denial and counter-narrative: Beijing dismissed involvement in the 2023 Matsu incidents, and in the Hong Tai 58 case China's public security bureau blamed Taiwanese smugglers (Xinhua 2025). This pattern — denial, alternative explanation, refusal of third-party investigation — is functionally analogous to the deniability management observed in Cases A and B. Taiwan's Coast Guard has responded by blacklisting nearly 100 China-linked vessels

suspected of operating under foreign flags (Indo-Pacific Defense Forum 2025).

Evidentiary outcomes vary but reinforce the cross-regional comparison. The 2023 Matsu incidents identified responsible vessels but produced no prosecutions due to insufficient evidence of intent (Ocon and Walberg 2025). The Shunxin 39 case yielded stronger indicators, including multiple MMSIs and AIS deactivation before the damage. The Hong Tai 58 conviction is globally unique: the court found deliberate severance but no proof of Chinese state direction (Chiang 2025). This judicial finding of intent in an analogous anchor-drag case weakens the plausibility of 'accidental dragging' as a general explanation for Chinese-linked vessels in the Baltic.

Taiwan has moved further than Europe in institutionalising cable-security responses. Cable protection is now integrated into its grey-zone doctrine (Taiwan's Ocean Affairs Council 2026; Lee, Hamacher, and Wang 2025), and ten domestic submarine cables were designated critical infrastructure in 2025 (Tsai and Hetherington 2026), preceding the EU's 2026 Cable Security Toolbox (European Commission 2026b). The Coast Guard's 100-vessel watch list represents a proactive surveillance posture not yet matched in Europe (Indo-Pacific Defense Forum 2025). However, the absence of diplomatic relations with China prevents Taiwan from pursuing the cable-diplomacy and boarding-protocol mechanisms available in principle to European states.

Within the grey-zone operation framework, the doubly decisive test is inapplicable for the same structural reasons as in the Baltic: investigators cannot access suspect vessels or electronic evidence. The hoop tests are passed more clearly in Taiwan. Chinese-linked vessels were present at every incident; the frequency of cases — 36 between 2019–2023, five in 2025 — is incompatible with global accident baselines; and China's consistent denial satisfies the deniability-management criterion. Smoking-gun evidence is absent, as predicted by the deniability architecture. The Hong Tai 58 conviction comes closest but still lacks proof of state

direction, consistent with the pattern observed in the Baltic. Straw-in-the-wind indicators are stronger in Taiwan than in either Baltic case individually. Shunxin 39's dual flags, six MMSIs, and AIS deactivation (Wang 2025; Chiang 2025) mirror the Newnew Polar Bear's identity manipulation; Taiwanese authorities intercepted Chinese research vessels allegedly collecting precise seabed cable data (Blanchard 2026), suggesting intelligence preparation; and the rising incident frequency aligns with deliberate probing rather than random accidents. Read alongside the Baltic pattern, these indicators significantly raise the probability of systematic disruption across both theatres.

4.4 Cross-Case Synthesis

The cross-case synthesis points to consistency across the five dimensions. On physical facts, in all cases, Chinese-linked commercial vessels are placed at cable damage sites by AIS data at the relevant times; in all cases, anchor dragging is the mechanism. In Cases A and B, the physical evidence — drag trails, recovered anchors, SHK findings — is robust and not seriously contested. The anomalous features of the Yi Peng 3 anchor drag represent the strongest physical evidence of non-accidental behaviour in the European cases.

The pattern of attribution and access management is consistent across all cases. China acknowledges physical causation only after extended delay and external pressure; denies intent; and manages investigative access to prevent European authorities from obtaining the electronic evidence most likely to establish intent. This pattern is too consistent across multiple incidents and multiple vessels to be coincidental. It is more parsimoniously explained by deliberate deniability management.

Furthermore, all cases produce the same evidentiary structure: physical causation confirmed, intent unresolved, investigation structurally constrained. This is not a coincidence of evidence scarcity — it is a structural feature of how the investigations have been managed. The SHK's

(2025) explicit acknowledgement that some facts contradict the accident explanation in the Yi Peng 3 case represents the closest any official investigation has come to expressing evidentiary doubt about the accident hypothesis.

European responses have escalated across the cases: from relatively muted reaction in October 2023 to the seizure of the Eagle S by Finland on Christmas Day 2024, indicating that European states are now willing to use coercive measures against suspected sabotage vessels, a shift from the passive monitoring posture of the Yi Peng 3 standoff.

Regarding fit with the grey-zone framework, across all cases the hoop tests for the grey-zone operations hypothesis are passed; smoking-gun evidence is absent; and the cumulative weight of straw-in-the-wind evidence — consistent pattern, consistent deniability management, consistent anomalous vessel behaviour, consistent evidentiary obstruction — points toward deliberate rather than accidental causation with increasing confidence across successive incidents.

5. Towards a Revised Typology

Section 5.1 draws the empirical findings together to develop a revised typology of Chinese influence in Europe that incorporates physical grey-zone operations as a distinct and analytically separable category. Section 5.2 points out the discovery of a new analytical dimension through inductive analysis.

5.1 The Revised Typology of Chinese Influence in Europe

The empirical cases do not fit any of the existing four categories of Chinese influence in Europe without significant distortion. Economic influence frameworks analyse Chinese activity through the logic of inducement and dependency creation — physical disruption operates

through cost imposition rather than benefit provision. Political influence frameworks are oriented toward changing minds and preferences — cable cutting targets operational capability rather than political cognition. Information frameworks are cognitive in orientation — physical disruption in maritime waters is not a digital or informational act, even if it has informational effects. The infrastructure-as-positioning framework comes closest, but it treats infrastructure as a passive strategic asset whose disruption potential is latent rather than activated. The Baltic incidents represent activated rather than latent infrastructure disruption.

The central typological claim of this paper is therefore that Chinese influence activity in European waters since 2023 has crossed a qualitative threshold requiring recognition of a fifth category in the analytical framework: physical grey-zone operations. Physical grey-zone operations, as proposed here, are defined as the deliberate use of physical force or physical disruption against an adversary's critical infrastructure or territorial integrity, conducted through commercial or civilian proxies, in a manner designed to maintain plausible deniability, avoid the threshold of armed attack under international law, and frustrate attribution and accountability through jurisdictional management. The category is distinguished from the four existing categories of Chinese influence by three defining features: physical mechanism, proxy instrumentalisation, and systematic deniability architecture.

Physical mechanism: unlike cognitive or relational instruments, physical grey-zone operations produce material damage regardless of attribution. The Baltic cases imposed hundreds of millions of euros in infrastructure repair and security costs — borne by European states whether or not China was ever formally held responsible.

Proxy instrumentalisation: commercial shipping vessels under flag-state jurisdiction were used as coercive instruments, limiting coastal states' enforcement powers. Flag-state jurisdiction ensures investigative access depends on the perpetrating state's cooperation — structurally

analogous to the use of unmarked soldiers in Russian hybrid operations or paramilitary fishing fleets in Chinese South China Sea grey-zone activity (Renz 2016; Erickson and Martinson 2019).

Systematic deniability architecture: the consistent pattern across both Baltic cases — delayed admission, attribution to accident, restricted investigative access, non-compliance with legal aid requests, routing to avoid European jurisdiction — constitutes structured practices designed to prevent formal legal accountability. The same template applied by different vessels and companies across both incidents indicates an underlying strategic logic.

Physical grey-zone operations should be understood as analytically distinct from but operationally connected to the other four categories of Chinese influence. Table 4 illustrates how the fifth category relates to the existing framework.

Table 4. Revised Typology of Chinese Influence in Europe

Category	Primary mechanism	Target	Deniability logic
Economic influence	Inducement, dependency creation	Political decisions, trade relations	Not required; operates openly
Political / elite capture	Co-optation, persuasion, party ties	Political cognition and preferences	Partial; operates through intermediaries
Information / FIMI	Narrative manipulation, amplification	Public opinion, institutional trust	Central; laundering through intermediaries
Infrastructure positioning	Ownership, access, dual-use presence	Structural dependency, leverage	Partial; commercial framing

Category	Primary mechanism	Target	Deniability logic
Physical grey-zone operations (proposed)	Material disruption through civilian proxies	Operational capability, deterrence signalling	Systematic; flag-state jurisdiction exploitation

Two analytical observations follow from this table. First, the fifth category is the only one in the existing framework that imposes direct operational costs regardless of attribution — the other four categories depend on their effects being perceived and processed by target actors, while physical disruption produces material consequences independent of political cognition. Second, physical grey-zone operations belong to the only category that systematically exploits the legal architecture of international maritime law as a deniability mechanism. The flag-state jurisdiction principle is a diplomatic and legal inconvenience for European investigators. It makes the fifth category uniquely difficult to deter, prosecute, or attribute under existing legal frameworks.

5.2 The Russia-China Nexus as an Additional Analytical Dimension

The empirical analysis identified a dimension that the existing typology of Chinese influence in Europe does not address: the possibility of operational coordination between Chinese and Russian actors in the conduct of physical grey-zone operations. Western intelligence assessments (Pancevski 2024a, 2024c; US Indo-Pacific Command 2024) reported in connection with the Yi Peng 3 case suggested that the ship's Chinese captain may have been induced by Russian intelligence, rather than instructed by Chinese state authorities. The Swedish National China Centre's (2025) analysis systematically examined four hypotheses about the level of authorisation and coordination, ranging from Zhongnanhai-directed sabotage to lower-level

Russia-China actor coordination without central authorisation.

Regardless of which hypothesis proves correct, the Russia-China nexus dimension has significant analytical implications. The existing literature on Chinese influence in Europe treats China as a unitary actor pursuing its own interests through its own instruments. If Chinese commercial vessels are being instrumentalised by Russian intelligence — whether with or without Beijing's authorisation — then the typology of Chinese influence in Europe must be supplemented by an account of how Chinese and Russian hybrid activities interact, complement, and potentially converge. This is a genuinely new analytical challenge that existing frameworks in either the Chinese influence literature or the Russian hybrid warfare literature are not equipped to address.

For the purposes of this paper's typological contribution, the Russia-China nexus does not disqualify the fifth category: whether the Newnew Polar Bear and Yi Peng 3 incidents were directed by Chinese state actors, Russian intelligence, or some combination of lower-level actors from both systems, the physical mechanism, proxy structure, and deniability architecture remain structurally identical. This nexus dimension suggests that future research should disaggregate the fifth category further, distinguishing between Chinese state-directed physical operations, Russian-orchestrated proxy use of Chinese commercial vessels, and joint or lower-level hybrid coordination — distinctions with significant implications for both attribution methodology and policy response.

6. Policy Implications

Based on empirical findings, this paper develops policy implications across four domains: jurisdictional reform, intelligence and attribution, deterrence, and diplomatic engagement with Beijing.

6.1 Legal and Jurisdictional Reform

The most acute policy gap exposed by the Baltic cable incidents is legal. As SIPRI's Pierre Thévenin (2025) has argued, the 1982 UNCLOS does not automatically grant a coastal state the authority to board and search a foreign vessel suspected of damaging submarine cables in its Exclusive Economic Zone (EEZ) — that authority depends on flag-state cooperation. The *Yi Peng 3* case demonstrated precisely what this means in practice: European states could surround the vessel with naval assets for a month but could not compel boarding, crew interview, or access to the VDR that would have provided the most probative evidence of intent.

This jurisdictional gap has been made even more explicit by subsequent legal proceedings. In October 2025, the Helsinki District Court dismissed charges against the captain of the *Eagle S* (Qiu 2025) — a vessel that dragged its anchor through the Gulf of Finland on Christmas Day 2024, severing multiple cables — ruling that Finland lacked jurisdiction because the incident occurred in its EEZ rather than its territorial waters. The court treated the episode as an incident of navigation under UNCLOS Article 97, which limits penal proceedings to the flag state or the nationality of the accused (Qiu 2025). This reasoning, if widely applied, effectively renders EEZ cable damage by foreign-flagged vessels immune from coastal state prosecution.

The policy implication is therefore clear and urgent: European states require legislative reform at both national and EU level to extend coastal state enforcement jurisdiction to suspected infrastructure sabotage in the EEZ, or to create alternative legal mechanisms — such as reframing systematic cable sabotage as piracy under UNCLOS Articles 101 and 105, as proposed by Hartmann (2025) — that do not depend on flag-state cooperation. SIPRI's (2025) commentary has argued that such reforms are achievable within the existing UNCLOS framework, which as a framework convention gives states considerable latitude in how they implement EEZ provisions. The EU's Cable Security Toolbox (European Commission 2026b)

does address deterrence through sanctions and diplomatic measures against hostile actors, but it does not directly resolve the jurisdictional gap in criminal investigation.

6.2 Intelligence, Attribution, and Evidence Preservation

The consistent pattern across Baltic cable incidents is that European states have strong circumstantial evidence of deliberate disruption but cannot produce the level of proof required for criminal prosecution or formal diplomatic attribution. This gap has two sources: the restricted access problem (China controls the evidence on board its vessels) and the timeliness problem (delays in boarding mean that electronic evidence can be wiped or overwritten before investigators arrive).

Both problems require anticipatory rather than reactive solutions. On the restricted access problem, the policy implication is pre-emptive: AIS monitoring infrastructure should be augmented with continuous seabed monitoring capabilities — hydrophone networks, permanent sensor arrays, and real-time cable integrity monitoring — that generate an independent evidentiary record of vessel behaviour and cable condition at the moment of damage, without requiring physical access to the suspect vessel. The EU's Cable Security Toolbox (European Commission 2026b) allocates €20 million for monitoring tools capable of detecting damage and tracking conditions under the sea, with a Baltic Sea pilot as the first phase. This is a meaningful first step, though the focus appears primarily on rapid damage detection rather than forensic-quality attribution evidence.

6.3 Deterrence and Response

The current European response to Baltic cable incidents has been primarily reactive: investigations opened after the fact, diplomatic notes delivered after vessels have departed, legal proceedings that courts then dismiss for jurisdictional reasons. The cumulative effect is a

deterrence posture of near-zero credible threat of accountability — precisely the condition that grey-zone operation is designed to exploit.

Finland's seizure of the Eagle S on Christmas Day 2024 represents the most significant shift in European response posture to date. Rather than surrounding the vessel and waiting for diplomatic permission to board, Finnish authorities seized and boarded the ship on the basis of suspected EEZ cable damage, effectively asserting broader jurisdictional authority than existing UNCLOS interpretation supports. The Helsinki District Court's subsequent dismissal of charges for jurisdictional reasons demonstrates the legal fragility of this approach in its current form (Qiu 2025), but the political and strategic signal was important: European states are willing to use coercive maritime enforcement even at legal risk. The policy implication is to translate this political willingness into durable legal authority, so that seizure decisions can be legally sustained rather than subsequently dismissed.

Beyond individual enforcement incidents, deterrence requires communicating clear and credible consequences to potential perpetrators. The EU's Cable Security Toolbox (European Commission 2026b) explicitly includes deterrence, enforcing sanctions and diplomatic measures against hostile actors and the shadow fleet, making full use of the Hybrid Toolbox to address hybrid campaigns. This framing — connecting cable sabotage to the broader EU Hybrid Toolbox — is analytically and politically significant: it positions cable incidents as hybrid warfare subject to the full range of EU response instruments rather than as isolated maritime accidents (European Commission 2026c). The paper's typological contribution reinforces this positioning: if physical grey-zone operations belong to a recognised category of Chinese influence alongside FIMI and economic coercion, the full Hybrid Toolbox — including sanctions, asset freezes, and diplomatic counter-measures — becomes potentially applicable.

6.4 Diplomatic Engagement with China

Such engagement should be calibrated to the Russia-China nexus dimension identified in the empirical analysis. If Beijing is not directing Baltic cable incidents but is rather being implicated through the actions of Russian intelligence using Chinese commercial vessels, China has its own reputational and strategic interest in preventing its commercial fleet from being instrumentalised in ways that damage European relations. European diplomacy could leverage this interest — framing cable diplomacy not as accusation but as a shared interest in preventing a pattern of incidents that is causing disproportionate damage to European perceptions of China.

7. Conclusions

Without legislative reform at national and EU level to close this gap, European states will continue to face the same pattern: credible circumstantial evidence of disruption, no legally actionable response, and a deterrence posture that imposes minimal costs on perpetrators. The EU's Cable Security Toolbox (European Commission 2026b) and associated €347 million investment programme represent significant institutional progress, but they are primarily oriented toward resilience and repair rather than accountability and deterrence.

The paper's contribution is therefore both conceptual and practical: it names a phenomenon that existing frameworks cannot adequately describe, provides an analytical vocabulary for investigating it rigorously, and identifies the specific legal, intelligence, deterrence, and diplomatic reforms required to address it. In a rapidly evolving security environment where Chinese commercial vessels and Russian hybrid operations are converging in European waters, that contribution is both timely and necessary.

Three limitations shape the scope of this study. Attribution of deliberate intent remains legally unresolved in both Baltic cases; the argument rests on cumulative circumstantial evidence, not

proven state direction, and future proceedings or intelligence disclosures may refine the interpretation. The small-N empirical base is appropriate for theory-building but not generalisation; as incidents accumulate, the hypotheses advanced here become amenable to more systematic testing. Chinese-language sources from China remain inaccessible, meaning the analysis relies on Western official and policy sources with their own framing interests.

A deeper limitation concerns the plausibility of state-level attribution itself. It remains genuinely difficult to imagine a strong strategic motivation for the Chinese state to conduct deliberate physical coercion against European undersea infrastructure at this stage of its relationship with Europe. China's economic and diplomatic interests in Europe are substantial, and the reputational costs of confirmed sabotage would be severe. The motive, in conventional strategic terms, is weak. Yet if the pattern documented in this paper reflects deliberate action — as the cumulative evidence suggests — one interpretive possibility is that China is not primarily seeking to impose costs on Europe but rather testing the operational viability of a new category of hybrid tactic: probing European investigative capacity, jurisdictional limits, and political resolve under conditions of managed deniability. On this reading, the Baltic incidents may represent tactical experimentation rather than strategic coercion, with the true audience being China's own security establishment rather than European policymakers. Future research should monitor whether the pattern continues, escalates, or is abandoned — since trajectory over time is itself evidentially significant for distinguishing deliberate probing from coincidental commercial incidents.

These limitations point to three priorities for future research. First, dedicated analytical treatment of the Russia-China nexus, which neither the Chinese influence nor the Russian hybrid warfare literature is currently structured to investigate. Second, legal experts can develop legal attribution methodology for maritime infrastructure incidents under conditions of flag-

state jurisdiction and deliberate deniability management. Third, cross-regional comparative work extending the analysis beyond the Baltic and Taiwan to assess whether the same pattern of mechanism, deniability management, and diplomatic containment is observable in other maritime theatres where Chinese-linked vessel behaviour near undersea infrastructure has been noted. Fourth, future research should examine whether the physical grey-zone operation category extends beyond maritime to aerial domains, with particular attention to the wave of drone incidents over European critical infrastructure and military installations since 2022. These incidents — including unregistered drone overflights of Swedish nuclear facilities and Romanian border areas, as well as drone intrusions over UK infrastructure sites — share the defining structural features of physical grey-zone operations: deliberate physical effect, ambiguous-status platform, and systematic prevention of attributable evidence. Unlike the Baltic cable cases, where a Chinese actor is implicated, the drone incidents are more plausibly attributed to Russian or Russian-linked proxies. Comparative analysis of these two streams would help determine whether physical grey-zone operations represent a general operational convergence across authoritarian actors, or whether the maritime and aerial variants reflect distinct strategic logics and organisational origins.

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References

- Andersson, P., B. Jerdén and A. von Sydow. 2025. *What the Yi Peng 3 cable-cutting incident reveals about China-Russia relations*. Swedish National China Centre. <https://kinacentrum.se/en/analyses/what-the-yi-peng-3-cable-cutting-incident-reveals-about-china-russia-relations/>
- Aukia, J. 2021. *China as a hybrid influencer: Non-state actors as state proxies*. Helsinki: European Centre of Excellence for Countering Hybrid Threats. <https://www.hybridcoe.fi/publications/hybrid-coe-research-report-1-china-as-a-hybrid-influencer-non-state-actors-as-state-proxies/>
- Bachulska, A., I. Karásková and K. Szatters. 2026. *Borrowed mouths and laundered messages: China's influence playbook in Europe*. Berlin: European Council on Foreign Relations. <https://ecfr.eu/publication/borrowed-mouths-and-laundered-messages-chinas-influence-playbook-in-europe/>
- Benner, T., J. Gaspers, J. Weidenfeld, M. Ohlberg, L. Poggetti and K. Shi-Kupfer. 2018. *Authoritarian advance: Responding to China's growing political influence in Europe*. Berlin: GPPi/MERICS. <https://merics.org/en/external-publication/authoritarian-advance-responding-chinas-growing-political-influence-europe>
- Bennett, A. 2010. 'Process tracing and causal inference.' In *Rethinking social inquiry: Diverse tools, shared standards*, edited by H. Brady and D. Collier, 207–220. Lanham, MD: Rowman and Littlefield.
- Bermingham, F. 2024. 'Beijing admits Hong Kong-flagged ship destroyed key Baltic gas pipeline.' *South China Morning Post*, 12 August. <https://www.scmp.com/news/china/diplomacy/article/3274120/china-admits-hong->

hong-flagged-ship-destroyed-key-baltic-gas-pipeline-accident

Besh, S. and E. Brown. 2024. *Securing Europe's subsea data cables*. Washington, DC: Carnegie

Endowment for International Peace.

<https://carnegieendowment.org/research/2024/12/securing-europes-subsea-data-cables>

Blanchard, B. 2026. 'Taiwan coast guard uses force to repel Chinese research vessel illegal

operations.' *Baird Maritime*, 11 May. <https://www.bairdmaritime.com/security/non->

[naval-security/taiwan-coast-guard-uses-force-to-repel-chinese-research-vessels-](https://www.bairdmaritime.com/security/non-naval-security/taiwan-coast-guard-uses-force-to-repel-chinese-research-vessels-illegal-operations)

[illegal-operations](https://www.bairdmaritime.com/security/non-naval-security/taiwan-coast-guard-uses-force-to-repel-chinese-research-vessels-illegal-operations)

Bonnet, P., E. F. Di Girolamo, A. Pagano, B. Velazquez and E. Zaurino. 2026. *From openness*

to vulnerability: Mapping the EU's foreign dependencies and geopolitical exposure.

London: Centre for Economic Policy Research.

[https://cepr.org/voxeu/columns/openness-vulnerability-mapping-eus-foreign-](https://cepr.org/voxeu/columns/openness-vulnerability-mapping-eus-foreign-dependencies-and-geopolitical-exposure)

[dependencies-and-geopolitical-exposure](https://cepr.org/voxeu/columns/openness-vulnerability-mapping-eus-foreign-dependencies-and-geopolitical-exposure)

Brands, H. 2016. *Paradoxes of the gray zone*. Philadelphia: Foreign Policy Research Institute.

<https://www.fpri.org/article/2016/02/paradoxes-gray-zone/>

Bryant, M. and P. Sauer. 2024. 'Swedish police focus on Chinese ship after suspected undersea

cable sabotage.' *The Guardian*, 20 November.

[https://www.theguardian.com/world/2024/nov/20/sweden-denmark-undersea-cable-](https://www.theguardian.com/world/2024/nov/20/sweden-denmark-undersea-cable-sabotage-navy-investigation)

[sabotage-navy-investigation](https://www.theguardian.com/world/2024/nov/20/sweden-denmark-undersea-cable-sabotage-navy-investigation)

Chen, Y.-W. 2020. 'The making of the Finnish Polar Silk Road: Status in spring 2019.' In

International flows in the Belt and Road Initiative context, edited by H. K. Chan, F. K.-

S. Chan and D. O'Brien, 193–216. London: Palgrave Macmillan.

- Chen, Y.-W. and Y.-F. Hao. 2020. 'Czech perception of the rise of China: A survey among university students.' *Asia Europe Journal* 18 (1): 157–175.
- Chen, J. Y.-W. and D. Ristivojević. 2023. 'Global-local dynamics in the Belt and Road Initiative projects.' *The Asia Pacific Journal: Japan Focus* 21 (4): 1–11.
- Chen, J. Y.-W. and M. Taylor. 2026. 'The Sino-Russian relationship and its implications across the Eurasian and Indo-Pacific strategic theatres.' *Communist and Post-Communist Studies*. <https://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.6640183>
- Chiang, G. C-H. 2025. *Countering China's subsea cable sabotage*. Washington, DC: Global Taiwan Institute. 19 March. <https://globaltaiwan.org/2025/03/countering-chinas-subsea-cable-sabotage/>
- Cullen, P., C. Juola, G. Karagiannis, K. Kivisoo, M. Normark, A. Rácz, J. Schmid and J. Schroefl. 2021. *The landscape of hybrid threats: A conceptual model (public version)*, edited by G. Giannopoulos, H. Smith and M. Theocharidou. Luxembourg: Publications Office of the European Union. <https://publications.jrc.ec.europa.eu/repository/handle/JRC123305>
- ERR. 2024. 'China admits container ship Newnew Polar Bear damaged undersea gas pipeline.' 12 August. <https://news.err.ee/1609422658/china-admits-container-ship-newnew-polar-bear-damaged-undersea-gas-pipeline>
- Erickson, A. S. and R. D. Martinson, eds. 2019. *China's maritime gray zone operations*. Annapolis: Naval Institute Press.
- European Commission. 2023. 'The Commission provides emergency funding to Finland in relation to the damage of the Balticconnector pipeline.' 18 December.

https://energy.ec.europa.eu/news/commission-provides-emergency-funding-finland-relation-damage-balticconnector-pipeline-2023-12-18_en

European Commission. 2026a. *China: EU trade relations with China. Facts, figures and latest developments.* https://policy.trade.ec.europa.eu/eu-trade-relationships-country-and-region/countries-and-regions/china_en

European Commission. 2026b. 'Commission increases submarine cable security with €347 million investment and new toolbox.' 5 February. <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/news/commission-increases-submarine-cable-security-eu347-million-investment-and-new-toolbox>

European Commission. 2026c. *Countering hybrid threats.* 19 March. https://www.eeas.europa.eu/eeas/eu-action-countering-hybrid-threats_en

European External Action Service. 2026. *Annual foreign information manipulation and interference reports.* https://www.eeas.europa.eu/eeas/1st-eeas-report-foreign-information-manipulation-and-interference-threats_en

European Parliament. 2023. *Security implications of China-owned critical infrastructure in the EU.* Brussels: European Parliament. [https://www.europarl.europa.eu/RegData/etudes/BRIE/2023/702592/EXPO_BRI\(2023\)702592_EN.pdf](https://www.europarl.europa.eu/RegData/etudes/BRIE/2023/702592/EXPO_BRI(2023)702592_EN.pdf)

Ewe, K. and I.-T. Chiang. 2025. 'Taiwan jails China captain for undersea cable sabotage in landmark case.' *BBC News*, 12 June. <https://www.bbc.com/news/articles/cwy3zy9jvd4o>

Fridman, O. 2018. *Russian 'hybrid warfare': Resurgence and politicization.* Oxford: Oxford University Press.

George, A. L. and A. Bennett. 2005. *Case studies and theory development in the social sciences*. Cambridge, MA: MIT Press.

Hackenbroich, J., A. Medunic and P. Zerka. 2022. *The economic weapon: How Europe can deter Russian aggression*. Berlin: European Council on Foreign Relations.

Hartmann, J. 2025. 'Piracy and undersea cables: An overlooked interpretation of UNCLOS?' *EJIL: Talk! — Blog of the European Journal of International Law*, 6 March. <https://www.ejiltalk.org/piracy-and-undersea-cables-an-overlooked-interpretation-of-unclos/>

Helsingin Sanomat. 2024. 'Kiina myöntää Newnew Polar Bear -laivan aiheuttaneen kaasuputkivaurion.' 12 August. <https://www.hs.fi/maailma/art-2000010625400.html>

Humpert, M. 2024. 'Russia now primary suspect in Yi Peng 3 Baltic Sea cable incident.' *gCaptain*, 16 December. <https://gcaptain.com/russia-now-primary-suspect-in-yi-peng-3-baltic-sea-cable-incident/>

Humpert, M. 2025. 'Newnew Polar Bear containership set to return to Europe via Arctic after 2023 Balticconnector incident.' *gCaptain*, 28 July. <https://gcaptain.com/newnew-polar-bear-containership-set-to-return-to-europe-via-arctic-after-2023-balticconnector-incident/>

Indo-Pacific Defense Forum. 2025. 'Taiwan strengthens patrols against China's undersea cable sabotage.' 28 September. <https://ipdefenseforum.com/2025/09/taiwan-strengthens-patrols-against-chinas-undersea-cable-sabotage/>

Joske, A. 2022. *Spies and lies: How China's greatest covert operations fooled the world*. Melbourne: Hardie Grant.

Kallionpää, K. 2023. 'Venäläinen rahtialus pysytteli koko viikonlopun Suomenlahdella kaasuputken vauriopaikan lähellä.' *Helsingin Sanomat*, 11 October. <https://www.hs.fi/suomi/art-2000009914694.html>

Lee, Y., F. Hamacher and A. Wang. 2025. 'Cable patrols stepped up amid new grey zone threat.' *Taipei Times*, 12 September. <https://www.taipetimes.com/News/taiwan/archives/2025/09/12/2003843668>

Lehto, E. 2023. 'Finland says gas pipeline likely broken by ship dragging anchor.' *Reuters*, 24 October. <https://www.reuters.com/world/europe/finland-retrieves-anchor-seabed-near-broken-gas-pipeline-2023-10-24/>

MapInfluenCE. 2026. <https://mapinfluence.eu>

Marine Insight. 2025. 'Taiwan jails Chinese captain for deliberately damaging vital undersea cable.' 13 June. <https://www.marineinsight.com/taiwan-jails-chinese-captain-for-deliberately-damaging-vital-undersea-cable/>

Mazarr, M. J. 2015. *Mastering the gray zone: Understanding a changing era of conflict*. Carlisle: Strategic Studies Institute, US Army War College. <https://press.armywarcollege.edu/monographs/428/>

Mercator Institute for China Studies (MERICS). 2023. *China global competition tracker no. 4*. 1 December. Berlin: MERICS.

Ministry of Foreign Affairs of the People's Republic of China. 2023. 'Foreign Ministry spokesperson Mao Ning's regular press conference on October 23, 2023.' https://www.fmprc.gov.cn/eng/xw/fyrbt/lxjzh/202405/t20240530_11347619.html

Ministry of Foreign Affairs of the People's Republic of China. 2024. 'Foreign Ministry

spokesperson Mao Ning's regular press conference on December 23, 2024.'

https://www.fmprc.gov.cn/eng/xw/fyrbt/lxjzh/202412/t20241223_11515858.html

Murphy, M. and G. Schaub. 2018. 'Sea of Peace or sea of war — Russian maritime hybrid warfare in the Baltic Sea.' *Naval War College Review* 71 (2): 122–148.

North Atlantic Treaty Organization. 2025. 'Statement of solidarity by the North Atlantic Council concerning the malicious cyber activities against the Czech Republic.' 28 May. <https://www.nato.int/en/about-us/official-texts-and-resources/official-texts/2025/05/28/statement-of-solidarity-by-the-north-atlantic-council-concerning-the-malicious-cyber-activities-against-the-czech-republic>

Norwegian Seismic Array (NORSAR). 2023. 'Seismic signal detected in the vicinity of the Balticconnector gas pipeline.' *NORSAR Press Statement*, 11 October. <https://www.norsar.no/news/seismic-signal-detected-in-the-vicinity-of-the-baltic-connector-gas-pipeline>

Nye, J. S. 2004. *Soft power: The means to success in world politics*. New York: PublicAffairs.

Ocean Affairs Council. 2026. <https://www.oac.gov.tw/ch/index.jsp>

Ocon, J. and J. Walberg. 2025. 'China's undersea cable sabotage and Taiwan's digital vulnerabilities.' *Global Taiwan Brief* 10 (11). <https://globaltaiwan.org/2025/06/taiwans-digital-vulnerabilities/>

Oertel, J. 2020. *The new China consensus: How Europe is growing wary of Beijing*. Berlin: European Council on Foreign Relations. 7 September. https://ecfr.eu/publication/the_new_china_consensus_how_europe_is_growing_wary_of_beijing/

Pancevski, B. 2024a. 'Russia suspected as Baltic undersea cables cut in apparent sabotage.' *The Wall Street Journal*, 20 November. <https://www.wsj.com/world/europe/russia-suspected-as-baltic-undersea-cables-cut-in-apparent-sabotage-801cb392>

Pancevski, B. 2024b. 'Chinese ship's crew suspected of deliberately dragging anchor for 100 miles to cut Baltic cables.' *The Wall Street Journal*, 29 November. <https://www.wsj.com/world/europe/chinese-ship-suspected-of-deliberately-dragging-anchor-for-100-miles-to-cut-baltic-cables-395f65d1>

Pancevski, B. 2024c. 'Brush with Russia in Baltic points to new flashpoint in NATO-Moscow shadow war.' *The Wall Street Journal*, 15 December. <https://www.wsj.com/world/europe/brush-with-russia-in-baltic-points-to-new-flashpoint-in-nato-moscow-shadow-war-08b5b182>

Poliisi (Finnish Police). 2023. 'The investigation is now focused on the role of the vessel Newnew Polar Bear.' 10 October. <https://poliisi.fi/en/-/the-investigation-is-now-focused-on-the-role-of-the-vessel-newnew-polar-bear>

Poliisi (Finnish Police). 2025. 'Cooperation in Balticconnector case to continue.' 9 May. <https://poliisi.fi/en/-/cooperation-in-balticconnector-case-to-continue>

Praks, H. 2025. *Russia's hybrid attacks in Europe: From deterrence to attribution to response*. Tallinn: International Centre for Defence and Security. <https://icds.ee/en/russias-hybrid-attacks-in-europe-from-deterrence-to-attribution-to-response/>

President of the Republic of Finland. 2025. 'Joint Statement of the Baltic Sea NATO Allies Summit.' 14 January. <https://www.presidentti.fi/en/joint-statement-of-the-baltic-sea-nato-allies-summit/>

- Qiu, W. 2025. 'Finnish court dismisses case against Eagle S — alleged sabotage of cables in the Baltic Sea.' *Submarine Networks*, 28 October. <https://www.submarinenetworks.com/en/nv/insights/finnish-court-dismisses-case-against-eagle-s>
- Radio Free Asia. 2023. 'China urges fair investigation into Baltic pipeline damage.' 26 October. <https://www.rfa.org/english/news/china/newnew-polar-bear-10262023050555.html>
- Rajavartiolaitos (Finnish Border Guard). 2024. 'Police: The police transfer tanker Eagle S to Kilpilahti.' 28 December. https://raja.fi/-/poliisi-eagle-s-sailioalus-siirretaan-kilpilahteen?languageId=en_US
- Raza, R. 2024. 'Bulk carrier Yi Peng 3 suspected in sabotage of undersea cables in the Baltic Sea.' *MarineTraffic Maritime News*, 20 November. <https://www.marinetraffic.com/en/maritime-news/16/general/2026/11649/bulk-carrier-yi-peng-3-suspected-in-sabotage-of-undersea-cab>
- Renz, B. 2016. 'Russia and hybrid warfare.' *Contemporary Politics* 22 (3): 283–300.
- Ringbom, H. 2025. 'New threats — old rules: Law of the Sea issues raised by suspected attacks on submarine infrastructure in the Baltic Sea.' *Ocean Development and International Law* 56 (3): 390–414.
- Ringbom, H. and A. Lott. 2024. 'Sabotage of critical offshore infrastructure: A case study of the Balticconnector incident.' In *Maritime security law in hybrid warfare*, edited by A. Lott, 155–194. Leiden: Brill.
- Sari, A. 2025. *Protecting maritime infrastructure from hybrid threats: Legal options*. Hybrid CoE Research Report 14. Helsinki: European Centre of Excellence for Countering

- Hybrid Threats. <https://www.hybridcoe.fi/publications/hybrid-coe-research-report-14-protecting-maritime-infrastructure-from-hybrid-threats-legal-options/>
- Stent, A. 2020. *Russia and China: Axis of revisionists?* Washington, DC: The Brookings Institution. <https://www.brookings.edu/articles/russia-and-china-axis-of-revisionists/>
- Stockholm International Peace Research Institute. 2025. 'A legislative route to combat sabotage of undersea cables: A Q&A with Pierre Thévenin.' *SIPRI Commentary*, 23 October. <https://www.sipri.org/commentary/topical-backgrounder/2025/legislative-route-combat-sabotage-undersea-cables>
- Swedish Accident Investigation Authority — Statens haverikommission (SHK). 2025. *SHK:s observationer ombord på det kinesiska lastfartyget YI PENG 3*. 15 April. <https://shk.se/>
- Torode, G. and J. Pomfret. 2026. 'Chinese captain pleads not guilty to Baltic Sea cable damage.' *Reuters*, 11 February. <https://www.reuters.com/world/china/chinese-captain-baltic-sea-cable-case-pleads-not-guilty-criminal-damage-charge-2026-02-11/>
- Tsai, Y.-J. and W. Hetherington. 2026. 'Amendments to protect undersea cables take effect.' *Taipei Times*, 12 January. <https://www.taipeitimes.com/News/taiwan/archives/2026/01/12/2003850453>
- US Indo-Pacific Command. 2024. *Legal Vigilance Update No. 14*. 22 December.
- Van Evera, S. 1997. *Guide to methods for students of political science*. Ithaca, NY: Cornell University Press.
- Walker, C. and J. Ludwig. 2017. *Sharp power: Rising authoritarian influence*. Washington, DC: National Endowment for Democracy. <https://www.ned.org/sharp-power-rising-authoritarian-influence-forum-report/>

Walker, C., S. Kalathil and J. Ludwig. 2020. 'The cutting edge of sharp power.' *Journal of Democracy* 31 (1): 124–137.

Wang, J. 2025. 'Chinese vessel cuts Taiwan internet cable in apparent sabotage.' *The Wall Street Journal*, 6 January. <https://www.wsj.com/world/asia/chinese-vessel-cuts-taiwan-internet-cable-in-apparent-sabotage-81e0d3b1>

Xinhua News Agency. 2025. 'Mainland police seek information on 2 suspected Taiwan smugglers.' 24 December. <https://english.news.cn/20251224/846ebcf7e79c49e3955c0abb1e311b07/c.html>

Yeh, A. 2025. *Testing the waters: Securing the UK's undersea cables against grey-zone threats*. London: China Strategic Risks Institute. 16 June. <https://www.csri.global/research/testing-the-waters>

YLE. 2024. 'Media: China admits cargo ship damaged Balticconnector pipeline.' 12 August. <https://yle.fi/a/74-20104546>